

1 **FOLK PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATIONS IN WESTERN**
2 **MEDITERRANEAN: IDENTIFICATION AND SAFETY OF CLAYS USED IN**
3 **PELOOTHERAPY**

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18 **Abstract**

19 *Ethnopharmacological relevance:* Clays are naturally occurring ingredients of many
20 natural health products, being included in most of ancient Mediterranean/European
21 medical texts and currently used to prepare therapeutic hot-muds (peloids) in several
22 thermal stations of the Mediterranean region. Clays are included in the formulation of
23 peloids as vehicles of the mineral-medicinal water, to obtain inorganic gels with
24 rheological and thermal properties suitable to be topically applied. Knowledge about
25 formulations and preparation procedures of these traditional medicines has been orally
26 transmitted since ancient times. Increasing recognition of the therapeutic utility of these
27 traditional and natural health care substances make necessary a full ethnopharmaceutic
28 research to ascertain those compositional characters that allow to establish quality
29 attributes and corresponding requirements for these materials and products, including
30 identity, purity, richness and safety.

31 *Materials and Methods:* Five clay samples (A, B, C, D and E) currently used in various
32 spa centers of southern European/Mediterranean countries were studied. X-Ray
33 diffraction (XRD) and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) data were used to assess sample
34 identity and richness. Elemental impurities and microbiological contaminants were also
35 determined and compared to normative limits. Particle size distribution was related to
36 their safety as powder materials.

37 *Results:* Samples A, C, D and E were identified as "high purity clay", while sample B
38 was identified as a mix of clay minerals and carbonates. The presence of carbonates in
39 this sample could compromise its suitability for pelotherapy. The studied clays meet the
40 main normative limits for metals impurities, with the exception of arsenic in sample A
41 and nickel in sample B. The samples comply with the microbiological limits proposed
42 by European legislation for medicinal products. According to the particle size of the
43 studied samples, prevention and control of dust exposure must be considered.

44 *Conclusions:* Despite their demonstrated longevity, the use of clays in traditional
45 medicine formulations as peloids greatly requires comprehension of their identity and
46 safety attributes. Continuity of these mineral substances as recognized health care
47 ingredients oblige to conduct interdisciplinary research to know the features that sustain
48 their traditional use in the preparation of medicines (ethnopharmaceutics).

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51 **1. Introduction**

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53 Traditional medicine involves the use of naturally occurring materials, mainly plants
54 and plant parts, but also inorganic materials, and in particular, clays. On behalf of their
55 healing properties, clays had been included in most of ancient Mediterranean/European
56 medical texts (De Vos, 2010), being used to treat skin pathologies (antiseptic
57 cataplasms), intestinal and stomach diseases (because of its astringent and adsorbent
58 properties) as well as in balneotherapy (Carretero et al., 2006).

59 Nowadays, modern medical care continues to use clays as highly significant health care
60 ingredients in industrial products (López-Galindo and Viseras, 2004) as well as in
61 natural remedies and dietary supplements (<http://www.dsld.nlm.nih.gov/dsld/>). In
62 western medicine, clays are used in patent medicinal products both as
63 pharmacologically inactive ingredients (abrasives, adsorbents, anticaking agents,
64 glidants, coating agents, opacifying agents, viscosity-increasing agents, emulsion
65 stabilizers, binders or suspending agents) (Viseras et al., 2007; Rowe et al., 2009), and
66 as pharmacologically active substances for the prevention, relief or cure of skin
67 pathologies, inflammations, contusions, and gastrointestinal disorders (López-Galindo
68 et al., 2011; Carretero et al., 2013).

69 In the last century, the use of clays in traditional European medicine had been
70 practically limited to medical hidrology (pelotherapy), with only some exceptions in
71 folk European (Pieroni et al., 2004) or migrant communities pharmacopoeias (Ellena et
72 al., 2012). Despites the longevity of clays as therapeutic ingredients (“Terra sigillata”
73 was probably the first patented medicine (Finkelman, 2006)), the dominant European
74 health care system, based on allopathic medicine, considers the use of clays in
75 traditional medicine as “complementary”, “alternative” or “non-conventional” remedies.
76 However, traditional medicine in developed countries is gaining popularity because it
77 offers less adverse effects and gentler means of managing chronic diseases (heart
78 disorders, cancer, diabetes...) in comparison with allopathic medicine (WHO, 2005). In
79 particular, several studies have analyzed the effectiveness of pelotherapy in patients
80 with rheumatic diseases versus allopathic therapies, noticing improvements in quality of
81 life or drug consume (Bostan et al., 2010; Fioravanti et al., 2012; Espejo Antúnez et al.,
82 2013). Pelotherapy involves the topical application of heated muds, constituted by
83 semisolid dispersions of clayey solid phases into mineral-medicinal waters (Veniale et
84 al., 2004). The selection of mud components, as well as their preparation and

85 application procedures follows traditional knowledge; the systems are frequently
86 prepared and used without proper understanding of their composition and quality
87 controls. However, confirmation (or refutation) of the possible effectiveness of these
88 natural health care products would absolutely require a scientific orientation focused to
89 assure applicable requirements (López-Galindo et al., 2007). It is desirable to design
90 and implement quality systems involving adequate control of raw materials, procedures
91 and final products.

92 Clays are included in the formulation of peloids as vehicles of the mineral-medicinal
93 water, to obtain inorganic gels with rheological and thermal properties suitable to be
94 topically applied. Knowledge about formulations and preparation procedures of these
95 traditional medicines has been orally transmitted since ancient times. The study of these
96 folk medicinal products involving identification of the ingredients and preparation
97 procedures fall into the concept of ethnopharmaceutics, as a part of ethnopharmacy
98 (Heinrich and Pieroni, 2001).

99 With these premises, this study is a first step in a much larger project aimed to address
100 the traditional therapeutic use of clays in European/Mediterranean countries in view of
101 establishing the minimum compositional requirements that should be comply to make
102 possible the evaluation of clinical efficacy of the treatments based on these natural
103 inorganic substances. For these purposes, and following pharmacopoeias and
104 international guidelines (www.healthcanada.gc.ca/nhp; ICH, 2013), this study aims to
105 determine compositional attributes of clay samples used in European/Mediterranean
106 thermal stations, including identity, purity, richness and safety of these natural
107 ingredients.

108

109 **2. Materials and methods**

110

111 Five clay samples (A, B, C, D and E) used to prepare peloids in 17 spa centres of three
112 southern European/Mediterranean countries (Italy, Spain and Tunisia) were studied.
113 Sample A was Volcangel[®] gifted by BENESA (Spain). Sample B was gifted under
114 confidential agreement. Sample C was Peloide Minerale[®] from SO.MI.ES. (Italy).
115 Sample D, came from Jebel Aidoudi deposits (Tunisia) and sample E was Innogel
116 LBB[®] clay purchased from Aplicaciones especiales del Vallés S.L. (Spain). Selected
117 samples were representative of the raw materials used by a large number of thermal

118 spas. All samples were milled, sieved (< 125 µm) and dried in oven (40 °C) before
119 carrying out any test.

120

121 **2.1. Identity and richness**

122

123 X-Ray diffraction (XRD) data and chemical analysis (major elements) were used to
124 asses sample identity and richness. The mineral quantification was based on the
125 measurements of peak areas in the diffractograms according to Biscaye (1965) and
126 Moore and Reynolds (1989), and corrected with chemical data (López-Galindo et al.,
127 1996) using the XPOWER[®] program (<http://www.xpowder.com/>) (Martín-Ramos,
128 2004). XRD analysis was done by using a Philips[®] X-Pert (Philips, Holanda)
129 diffractometer equipped with automatic slit (CuK α , 4-70° 2 θ , 6°/min, 40kV) both on
130 bulk random and oriented aggregated samples (glycolated and heated to 550°C). Major
131 elements were determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF), using a Bruker[®] S4 Pioneer
132 equipment, with a Rh X-ray tube (60 kV, 150 mA).

133

134 **2.2. Purity**

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136 **2.2.1. Trace elements**

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138 The following elements were analyzed by ICP/MS Perkin Elmer[®] SCIEX Elan-5000
139 equipment prior sample digestion with "aqua regia" (HNO₃ + 3HCl): Ag, As, Au, Ba,
140 Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mo, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se and Tl. Accuracy was in the 1-3 % range,
141 depending on the element amount. The analyses were carried out by Activation
142 Laboratories Ltd. (Canada).

143

144 **2.2.2. Microbiological contaminants**

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146 Microbiological tests were carried out according to European Pharmacopoeia methods
147 (EP 7.0, 2011). The analysis included total viable aerobic, contaminating fungi (yeast
148 and mould), *Salmonella spp.*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and
149 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

150

151 **2.3. Particle size distribution**

152 Particle size analysis was performed with a Malvern® Mastersizer 2000 LF
153 granulometer. Prior to the analysis, a few milligrams of powder sample were dispersed
154 in purified water and sonified for several minutes.

155

156 **3. Results and Discussion**

157

158 **3.1. Identity and richness**

159

160 Mineralogical compositions of the samples (Table 1) were determined on the basis of
161 XRPD patterns (Fig. 1) and chemical compositions (Table 2). Samples A, C, D and E
162 were identified as "high purity clays" as the sum of minerals assigned to this group
163 (smectites, kaolinite, illite and chlorite) was > 70% w/w. Sample B was identified as a
164 mix of clay minerals (illite, chlorite and kaolinite) and carbonates (calcite and
165 dolomite). Significant presence of carbonates (13% w/w) was also detected in sample C.
166 Several authors have pointed out the importance of presence of high content of clay
167 minerals (in particular smectites) in samples to be used in pelotherapy, because
168 rheological, thermal and chemical features associated to these minerals improve some
169 performances (Veniale et al., 2004; Carretero et al., 2007; Rebelo et al., 2011).
170 Carbonates can be considered as "inert" impurities, even if their high relative amount in
171 sample B could compromise its suitability for pelotherapy. Crystalline silica (quartz)
172 was also measured in all the studied samples. This mineral is usually present in all clay
173 deposits, but its occurrence in health care products must be reduced as much as possible
174 as it is classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as a
175 product with sufficient evidence of carcinogenicity in laboratory animals and limited
176 evidence in humans (Group 1) (IARC, 1997). In a most recent monograph, it has been
177 corroborated that crystalline silica in the form of quartz or cristobalite dust is
178 carcinogenic to humans (Group 1) (IARC, 2012). It must be pointed out that crystalline
179 silica did not show the same carcinogenic potency in all circumstances (IARC, 1997). In
180 particular, the association of quartz with clay minerals inhibits most adverse effects
181 (Duffin et al., 2001; Schins et al., 2002, Creutzenberg et al., 2008; Miles et al., 2008).

182

183 **3.2. Purity**

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185 **3.2.1. Trace elements**

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187 All the trace elements considered are naturally associated to mined materials. The
188 speciation and physicochemical state of these elements are important factors in
189 considering their bioavailability and toxicity. Most of the elements that can exert
190 adverse effects even at low concentration should be maintained within acceptable limits.
191 In absence of a specific legislation, the measured values of elemental impurities in the
192 studied samples were compared to the limits proposed for clays to be used as
193 pharmaceutical ingredients by European and USA pharmacopoeias (EP, 7.0., 2011;
194 USP 36 - NF 31, 2013), those recommended for topical products by the Natural Health
195 Product Directorate (NHPD) of Canada (www.healthcanada.gc.ca/nhp) and those
196 included in the "Guideline for elemental impurities" in drug products, recently issued by
197 the International Conference of Harmonization (ICH, 2013).

198 Pharmacopoeial impurities only refer to arsenic and lead content. As shown in Table 3,
199 all samples met the pharmacopoeial limits, with the exception of arsenic for sample A.
200 However, it must be pointed out that systemic absorption of arsenic via the skin is very
201 low (NRC, 1999; ATSDR, 2007). The use of sample A in pelotherapy is therefore
202 unlikely to be harmful, even if treatment to reduce arsenic would be desirable.

203 As regards of other significant elements with health concern, contents of Cd, Hg and Sb
204 were compared to limits proposed in NPHD guide for topical products (Table 3). All
205 samples meet the required limits for these elements. The presence of other elements
206 (Mo, Se, Co, Ag, Au, Tl, Ba, Cr, Cu, and Ni) with relative low toxicity or toxicity based
207 on route of administration were also evaluated and compared with limits included in
208 guide Q3D of ICH (Table 3). The Q3D guide defines relevant thresholds for elemental
209 impurities in raw materials (both actives and excipients) and medicinal products
210 administered by oral, parenteral and inhalatory routes. The studied samples meet the
211 required limits, with the exception of Co content. Topical exposure to Co induces
212 dermatitis (ATSDR, 2004). Nevertheless, it must be pointed that allergic topical effects
213 of Co appear mainly from exposure to the metal itself, rather than to aqueous Co salts
214 (Nielsen et al., 2000). Ni content in sample B was also greater than the required limit.
215 Allergic contact dermatitis is also frequently induced by Ni chlorate and sulfate
216 (ATSDR, 2005). Ni is a natural constituent of soil in concentrations ranging from 4 to
217 80 ppm (ATSDR, 2005). The presence on > 80 ppm of Ni in sample B should be take
218 into consideration, since human and animal studies showed that Ni can penetrate the
219 skin (Norgaard, 1955; Norgaard, 1957; Lloyd, 1980; Fullerton et al., 1986).

220 3.2.2. Microbiological contaminants

221

222 The presence of certain microorganisms in non-sterile preparations may have the
223 potential to adversely affect the health of the patients and must be consequently
224 carefully determined. Results of microbial examination of the studied samples were
225 compared to normative limits proposed by European legislation (EP 7.0., 2011) (Table
226 4). The limit for total aerobic microbial count is 10^3 CFU/g in "non-sterile substances
227 for pharmaceutical use", whereas for "non-sterile oral dosage forms containing raw
228 materials of natural (animal, vegetal o mineral) origin" it increases to 10^4 CFU/g,
229 reaching 10^5 CFU/g in some "herbal medicinal products". Similarly, the limit for
230 combined yeasts/moulds is in the range 10^2 CFU/g - 10^4 CFU/g, depending on the
231 nature of the starting material and the manufacturing process. None of the samples
232 exceeded the acceptance criteria for "herbal medicinal products". With exception of
233 sample A, the samples also complied with limits for "non-sterile oral dosage forms
234 containing raw materials of natural (animal, vegetal o mineral) origin". As regards of
235 pathogen microorganisms, all the samples complied with the required absence of
236 *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella spp.* and *Staphylococcus*
237 *aureus*.

238

239 3.3. Particle size

240

241 The granulometric distribution of the samples was almost unimodal with mean particle
242 diameters in the range 4.4 μm (sample D) – 16.7 μm (sample A) (Fig. 2). The
243 pathogenic inhalatory potential of particulate matters (dust) are related to their
244 composition, as for example the presence of crystalline silica or chemical impurities, as
245 discussed previously, but also to their physical properties, and in particular to the
246 particle size distribution (WHO, 1999). Depending on their size, particles of raw clay
247 materials used to prepare peloids could become hazardous to worker health, particularly
248 when suspended in air. The respirable dust range harmful to workers' health is defined
249 by those particles at, or below, the 10 μm size range (Cecala et al., 2012). Smaller
250 airborne particles of dust, which can remain suspended in air for hours, pose a greater
251 risk to the respiratory system when inhaled. Particles having a diameter of greater than
252 10 μm are expected to be deposited in the nasopharyngeal region, whereas particles
253 with diameter under 5 μm may achieve the bronchial and alveolar regions. Cumulative

254 particle size distribution of the studied samples (Fig. 3) was used to determine the
255 fraction of particles likely to be deposited in the alveolar region of the lungs when
256 inhaled (respirable dust). More than 99 % of the particles had a diameter under 100 μm
257 and consequently prevention and control of dust exposure must be considered.
258 Cumulative % of particles with diameters under 5 μm were noticeable, ranging from
259 27.4 (sample A) to 69.8 (sample D). Taking into account that studied samples also
260 present quartz contents $> 5\%$ w/w, strategies of controlling occupational exposure, as
261 well as implementation of control measures should be desirable.

262

263 **4. Conclusions**

264

265 Despite their demonstrated longevity and therapeutic effectiveness, the use of clays in
266 traditional medicine greatly requires comprehension of their action mechanism and
267 composition related effects. Continuity of these mineral substances as recognized health
268 care ingredients obliges to conduct interdisciplinary research to understand the features
269 that sustain their therapeutic uses. Accordingly to their mineralogical composition, the
270 studied samples were identified as "high purity clays" with important differences in
271 richness. In particular, the presence of carbonates in sample B characterizes this raw
272 material. As regards of the presence of mineral impurities with safety concerns, quartz
273 amounts in the samples was not relevant for patient's health, even if the presence of this
274 mineral would require adequate controls during the preparation stages of the thermal
275 muds to prevent any hazard in workers. Elemental impurities in the studied samples
276 were compared to the limits proposed in three related legislations, finding that As in
277 sample A and Ni in sample B should be reduced. The samples comply with the
278 microbiological limits proposed by European legislation. Finally, as regards of the
279 particle sizes of the studied samples, control of occupational exposure is advised.

280

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285

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415 **Tables**416 **Table 1.** Mineral composition (w/w %) of the studied samples.

	A	B	C	D	E
Smectites	65	traces	42	68	80
Quartz	5	13	10	5	7
Calcite	5	31	11	4	-
Albite	10	4	4	-	-
K-Feldspars	3	2	-	-	-
Kaolinite	traces	7	9	5	12
Illite	6	23	22	7	-
Clinoptilolite	6	-	-	-	-
Dolomite	-	6	2	-	-
Chlorite	-	12	-	-	-
Gypsum	-	traces	-	11	2

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419 **Table 2.** Major-element content (w/w %) of the studied samples.

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MnO	MgO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	LOI
A	56.71	11.17	3.36	0.05	12.62	3.81	2.89	1.47	0.37	0.10	7.11
B	33.82	11.37	4.39	0.06	4.17	19.66	0.62	2.43	0.44	0.12	22.00
C	48.64	17.23	6.52	0.18	2.35	7.97	1.26	2.46	0.76	0.15	10.90
D	45.83	17.23	6.67	0.03	2.03	6.32	3.14	1.72	0.96	0.29	8.56
E	50.98	18.63	9.31	0.03	2.42	1.00	2.33	1.20	1.35	0.14	10.80

420 LOI (loss on ignition)

421

422 **Table 3.** Trace elements (ppm, aqua regia digestion) in the samples with safety concerns accordingly to
423 European and USA pharmacopoeias (EP, USP); Canadian Natural Health Products Guide (NHPG) and
424 Q3D guideline (Q3DG).

425

Element (detection limit, ppm)	A	B	C	D	E	Acceptable limit (ppm)	Normative	Class
As (0.5)	15.6	3.8	4.4	5.0	1.8	≤ 8	EP, USP	
Pb ^a (0.1)	11.4	12.9	13.4	9.6	8.1	≤ 50		
Cd (0.1)	< 0.1	0.2	0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	3	NHPG	
Hg (0.01)	< 0.01	0.04	0.04	< 0.01	< 0.01	1		
Sb (0.1)	0.2	0.5	0.2	< 0.1	< 0.1	5		
Mo (0.1)	0.2	1.8	1.7	0.7	0.6	18		
Se (0.5)	0.7	1.7	0.9	1.3	1.4	17	Q3DG ^b	2A
Co (0.1)	5.9	13.8	19.2	12.7	12.9	5		
Ag (0.1)	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	17		
Au (0.01)	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	13	Q3DG ^b	2B
Tl (0.1)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.80		
Ba (1)	359	102	158	25	183	1300		
Cr (1)	16	76	58	101	86	1100	Q3DG ^b	3
Cu (0.1)	21.7	26.1	62.9	15.9	39.2	130		
Ni (0.1)	6.3	88.4	54.5	33.1	41.9	60		

426 ^a"Heavy metals" assay in European Pharmacopoeia match to Pb determination (EP 7.0, 2011).427 ^bOral limits in drug products, drug substances and excipients, accordingly to table A.2.2 of Q3D guide.

428 **Table 4.** Results of microbial examination of the samples and acceptance criteria for "Non-sterile
 429 substances" (NSS), "Oral dosage forms containing materials of natural origin" (MNO) and "Herbal
 430 medicinal products" (HMP) accordingly to European Pharmacopoeia.

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Microorganism (CFU/g)	A	B	C	D	E	NSS	MNO	HMP
Total aerobic microbial	14000	4400	3300	< 1000	10000	10 ³	10 ⁴	10 ⁵
Yeasts and Moulds	< 10	< 10	< 10	< 10	86	10 ²	10 ²	10 ⁴
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	A	A	A	A	A	-	-	-
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	A	A	A	A	A	A	-	-

432 A (absence)

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457 **Figures**

458 Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the studied samples.

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Figure 1.

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474 Fig. 2. Granulometric distribution of the samples.

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Figure 2.

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497 Fig. 3. Cumulative particle size distribution of the studied samples.

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Figure 3.